

**TEACHER OF THE DEPARTMENT OF PRESCHOOL-PRIMARY
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Topic: Pedagogical and psychological essence and axiological content of the formation of positive qualities.

Abstract: The issue of implementing innovative mechanisms for effective activity of students and approaches based on the development of their communication culture into practice is urgent in the world. The upbringing of a well-rounded person directly requires the formation of his moral and positive qualities on a scientific basis. This research work highlights new teaching methods for developing a culture of communication in students, cultivating their speech, and forming their creative potential and positive qualities based on values.

Keywords: axiology, virtue, positive virtue, coherence and continuity, consistency, relevance, skill, knowledge.

Introduction

The maturity of a modern person is determined not only by his knowledge, but also by his possession of high spiritual and moral qualities. In today's era of globalization and information technologies, the formation of internal beliefs and stable positive characteristics that can correctly direct a person remains a priority task of pedagogical theory and practice. In a number of reforms being implemented in the Republic of Uzbekistan, including the National Model of Personnel Training, the Law "On Education" and the words of the President, the idea of raising a perfect person, a selfless patriot and a qualified specialist occupies a central place. Raising a perfect person directly requires the formation of his moral and positive qualities on a scientific basis.

Analysis of literature on the topic

In the same context, the urgency of the need to deeply understand the pedagogical essence of personal qualities and study the mechanisms of their formation is

manifested. As the famous Russian pedagogue V.A. Sukhomlinsky noted, "the main goal of education is to make a person not only knowledgeable, but also highly moral." In particular, the theories of values and moral development of Western researchers, including M. Rokeach and L. Kohlberg, also show that positive qualities are not only a set of external norms, but also a system of internal motivation and beliefs.

Research methodology

The scope of ideas and considerations regarding the formation of positive qualities of students in the lessons of the native language and reading literacy is explained by the fact that the methods of communication, methods of teaching students are enriched with new conclusions.

In today's complex socio-cultural environment, the analysis of positive qualities of a person based on a structural approach is of great importance. The most effective way from a scientific point of view is to study virtues not simply as actions, but as the result of mutual integration of cognitive (cognitive), emotional (emotional-volitional) and practical (behavioral) components. Although the spiritual and moral aspects of personal development play a fundamental role in the work of Uzbek scientists O. Musurmonova, M. Mirkasimova and others, in the conditions of globalization there is a need to more clearly systematize pedagogical criteria such as stability, activity and transfer of qualities and improve the methodology for assessing them.

The problem of positive qualities and moral education has been of fundamental importance in the fields of pedagogy, psychology and philosophy. The works of such great scholars as Central Asian thinkers as Abu Nasr Farabi, Abu Rayhan Beruni, Alisher Navoi, Abdulla Avloni, widely covered the meaning and importance of such qualities as a perfect person, justice, hard work and patriotism. They created the spiritual and moral foundations for the full formation of the qualities of a person.

Abu Nasr Al-Farabi directly linked human perfection with moral qualities. In his pedagogical views, justice and intelligence are considered the highest qualities. Abu

Nasr Al-Farabi emphasized that “in order for a person to achieve happiness, it is necessary to form willpower qualities (for example, courage, chastity, justice) along with intellectual strength.” In his opinion, “a person can form stable moral habits by repeating positive actions of his own free will.”

Abu Rayhan Al-Biruni pays great attention to the qualities of the desire for knowledge, honesty, and hard work in his pedagogical views. He considered honesty, loyalty to his work, and justice to be the main virtues for a scientist and specialist. He noted that “a scientist must know and educate not only the secrets of nature, but also his own soul.” Al-Biruni considered work to be the main factor that enriches a person spiritually and strengthens positive qualities.

The great thinker, the sultan of the word, Mir Alisher Navoi, also repeatedly emphasized in his works that positive qualities are a mirror of a person's soul. His work "Mahbub ul-qulub" in particular is devoted to human morality and virtues, in which the thinker considered kindness, generosity (generosity) and patriotism to be the highest virtues. A. Navoi prioritized the personal example of a teacher (mentor) in the formation of decency and humanitarian qualities in a person. In his opinion, "true human qualities are manifested in practical actions such as helping others and showing compassion to the poor." This indicates the importance of the socio-moral (moral) component of positive qualities.

As a major representative of the Jadid movement in the formation of positive qualities, one of the founders of national pedagogy, Abdulla Avloni, also made a great contribution to the educational school through his pedagogical views. His work "Turkish Rose or Morality" is entirely devoted to the education of positive qualities. A. Avloni emphasized the need to "form such qualities as knowledge, discipline, cleanliness, honesty (honesty) from a young age, in the school system." He defined the goal of education as "teaching a person good manners that will be useful in this world and the hereafter." These views of Avloni express the need to combine the cognitive (knowledge) and emotional (feeling) components of positive qualities.

Conclusions and suggestions

The formation of positive qualities is an integrative process that ensures the psychological development of a student, provides for his understanding of high moral values and their application in his life, and is the main goal of pedagogy and psychology.

Based on the above ideas, we can draw the following conclusions: Creating favorable conditions for the formation and development of students' speech competencies through educational technologies; achieving the maximum mastery of educational materials; transforming and activating students into participants in the educational process; as a result of scientifically and methodologically correct organization of lessons based on a specific goal, students' speech development and systematic and coherent mastery of knowledge are achieved.

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